

Physics-inspired End-to-End Deep Learning for High-Performance Optical Fiber Transmission Links

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Abstract: We experimentally demonstrate the performance improvements obtained through End-to-End Deep Learning in noise and chromatic dispersion compensation of optical fiber transmission links when incorporating a physics-inspired activation function compared to state-of-the-art ReLU configurations. © 2022 The Authors

1. Introduction

The growing requirement in achieved information rate for short-reach fiber optic communication links, has fuelled novel transceiver Digital Signal Processing (DSP) designs based on Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) [1]. Particularly, autoencoder-based NNs have been recently brought into the spotlight, as their universal function approximation properties allow for end-to-end optimization of a fiber communication link and compensation of the chromatic dispersion and square-law detection induced non-linearities [2],[3]. Such systems have already showcased their credentials to increase the reach or enhance the data rate of Intensity Modulation/Direct Detection (IM/DD) links compared to pulse amplitude modulation systems with nonlinear equalizers [4].

In all these demonstrations, the choice of the activation function of the end-to-end system proceeds across the golden standard of digital NN implementations, where the ReLU and ReLU-variants dominate [2]-[4]. However, with ReLU-variants not originating from any physical non-linear optical system, these autoencoder models significantly deviate from the paradigm of physics inspired NNs [5]. The field of physics-inspired NNs combines deep learning and physics for modelling real physical systems [5], embedding the knowledge of physical laws into the NN learning process. either through the introduction of appropriate loss functions and/or through the use of nonlinear activations that draw their response from physical systems. In this realm, a nonlinear activation function that can be implemented in the optical domain and naturally counteract noise degradation and dispersion-induced nonlinearities can benefit End-to-End Deep Learning (DL) systems. Nevertheless, the implementation and performance of non-linear optical phenomena-based activation functions in End-to-End optical transmission links has not been reported to date.

In this paper, we investigate the performance of End-to-End DL optical fiber transmission links when employing a nonlinear activation function that is effectively derived from the physical mechanisms encountered in non-linear

Fig. 1 (a) Optical link IM/DD End-to-End model comprising transmitter and receiver ANN, with 4 communication channels b) ReLU, CReLU and Photonic Sigmoid activation functions. c) Experimental Setup of the End-to-End link evaluation for 3 of the 4 communication channels.

semiconductor physics and has been experimentally demonstrated in [6] as a sigmoid-variant activation, termed as “photonic” sigmoid. An extensive simulation analysis backed by experimental data of 48 Gb/s for fiber links at up to 42 km has been carried out, validating that the photonic sigmoid-based autoencoder outperforms the ReLU-based configurations commonly employed in state-of-the-art End-to-End DL systems, allowing for a BER of 10^{-6} transmission for 2.5x longer fiber links.

2. End-to-End communication link analysis

We begin our analysis by developing a simulation model of an autoencoder-based End-To-End fiber transmission link, based on the guidelines provided in [2] also depicted in Fig. 1 (a) where the corresponding simulation parameters presented at the inset table. In order to gain a deeper insight of the autoencoder operation for different activation functions, we simulate the network over four different communication channels towards analysing and quantifying the stand-alone and combined effects of chromatic dispersion and channel originating noise: (i) the AWGN channel, where an optical fiber with zero chromatic dispersion is considered. (ii) The Dispersive channel, where the optical channel noise is set to zero. (iii) The combined Dispersive channel with constant AWGN, which corresponds to an automatic gain amplified transmission link that maintains a constant output power level at its Rx front-end. (iv) The Dispersive channel with AWGN, which corresponds to a regular short reach transmission link. Two configurations of activation functions were assessed, in the first the ReLU was applied in all input and hidden layer neurons and the Clipping ReLU (CReLU) was used on Tx final layer, while in the second, the Photonic Sigmoid activation function [6] was applied in all layers. A schematic representation of the activation functions is depicted in Fig. 1 (b).

In conjunction with the simulation-based analysis, we developed an experimental setup depicted in Fig. 1 (c), which allows the assessment of the three different communication channels, excluding the zero AWGN channel that could not be physically constructed as it would require zero noise levels. The AWGN channel is experimentally realized through an attenuator, that introduces excess loss to the signal path and as such decreases the optical power at the Rx. The combined Dispersive channel with constant AWGN, corresponds to an automatic gain EDFA with constant output power. No modifications were required for the Dispersive channel with AWGN. During the experimental validation a randomly generated bit-sequence of 5×10^4 samples was launched to the Tx NN resulting in a 48 Gb/s-8 GBaud/s signal. At the Rx NN side, prior to the BER estimation, the NN was re-trained to account for the dynamic distortions arising at the physical link. Finally, the finite memory of the deployed DAC sets the maximum number of transmittable symbols, corresponding to a minimum estimable BER of 1.2×10^{-6} .

Figure 2 (a)-(d) illustrates the acquired simulation and experimental results for the four communication channels. As can be observed, the photonic sigmoid activation function outperforms the ReLU/CReLU for all the channel configurations revealing that physics-inspired activation functions outperform classical implementations in related optical non-linear phenomena tasks, such as dispersion and noise compensation in IM/DD systems.

Fig. 2 (a)-(d) BER values for the 4 communication channels and 2 configuration of activation functions i.e Photonic Sigmoid or ReLU/CReLU.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the EC H2020 NEBULA (871658) and ALLEGRO (101092766) projects.

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